

**COMPARISON OF THE BJP AND CONGRESS MANIFESTOES FOR THE 2019 LOK
SABHA ELECTION**

Divya Dahiya Research Fellow Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Udaipur
Email: divya.dahiya18@gmail.com

Abstract:

Electoral manifestoes play a pivotal role in presenting the visions of parties in a democracy. They are a compilation of valid positions of parties on diverse issues of importance to the country and the electorate. They define issues and set forth a larger framework as campaign material. The power of written words is greater than unwritten, vague, oral promises.

It has been a usual practice that political parties release their manifestoes at the time of general elections so that electorates are familiarised with the policies and programs of the party. Though a wide range of policy matters and programs are used to find a place in the manifestoes, only a few have a direct concern for the general public. In this paper, I have done a comparative analysis of key promises made by BJP and Congress in their election manifestoes.

Key Words: Manifesto, Political Parties, Election

Election Manifesto- Concept and Relevance

A Manifesto can be defined as a published declaration of the intentions, goals, or perspectives of an individual, group, political party, or government whosoever issues it. In the parliamentary form of government, manifestoes are an important aspect of Democratic electoral politics as statements of party's ideology, motives, and policy.

Cambridge Dictionary defines a manifesto as a written statement of the belief, aims, and policies of an organization especially a political party. Hence, an election manifesto is a public document comprising a declaration of the ideology, intentions, policies, and programs of a political party.

Party manifestoes form the most important source of a political party's aim and object as well as its approach to bring about social, political, and economic change, Party manifestoes deal with complex societal issues. In a way, the manifestoes represent what has been generally attributed to the definition of ideology, i.e. 'ideas about society.

Here are key promises from the election manifestoes by the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) and the Congress for the 2019 Lok Sabha elections on common points:

1. Economy

The BJP aspires to make India the third-largest economy of the world by 2030 and of a dollar 5 trillion economy by 2025. BJP has proposed reforms like improving India's rank in ease of doing business, dispute resolution mechanism for MSME'S and single window compliance. It has also proposed making technical and procedural defaults under the Companies Act as civil liberties. Congress has proposed its economic philosophy based on embracing the idea of an open and liberal market economy. Its two principal goals are wealth creation and the Welfare of all sections of the people. It has also promised autonomy of the RBI, scrapping of the Angel tax for Start-Ups and Rehabilitation plan for MSMEs. It has said to increase the share of manufacturing to 25% ,reviewing foreign trade policy and all rules,regulations and laws related to governing investment.

2. Healthcare

The BJP has promised to make Healthcare accessible by setting up 150000 health and Wellness centers by 2022. Congress has promised to double the total government expenditure on health care to 3% of GDP by the year 2023-24. BJP wants to ensure full immunization coverage for all the children and pregnant women by 2022. Congress has promised to enact the Right to Healthcare Act and free public hospitals model to ensure Universal Healthcare. Congress has said to establish trauma and emergency centers on all national and state highways.

3. Agriculture

The BJP has promised to double the income of farmers by 2022. Pradhanmantri Kisan Samman Nidhi Yojana would be extended to cover all the farmers in the country. Congress has pledged to present a separate Kisan budget for agriculture. It also promised to establish National Commission on agricultural development and planning and the commission on marginal farmers and agricultural labor.

The BJP has promised to invest rupees 25 lakh crore to improve the productivity of the farm sector. Congress has said that that is a civil liability and criminal proceedings would not be instituted against a farmer who is unable to pay his or her debt.

The BJP wants to make the Pradhan Mantri fasal Bima Yojana Crop Insurance Scheme voluntary for farmers whereas the Congress set to completely redesign the scheme while both the parties focus on the extension of modern warehousing warehouses, cold storage and food processing facilities. The BJP wants to establish national warehousing along the national highways. Organic farming also finds a place in both manifestoes. The BJP has proposed to promote organic Ecotourism in the vicinity of organic farming. Congress has promised to restore the land acquisition rehabilitation and resettlement act and the forest rights act in their original form.

4. Climate change

During the 2019 Lok Sabha elections, promises to tackle air pollution were featured in the manifestoes of the major political parties, such as setting deadlines, introducing new emission standards, promoting electric vehicles. While the BJP promised to turn the National Clean Air Programme (NCAP) into a 'mission', the Congress promised to reinforce the NCAP to tackle pollution. Both the BJP and Congress promised to create a new ministry of water to resolve the water crisis. This is a noticeable change from the 2014 elections.

5. Infrastructure

The BJP wants to provide a pucca house for every family, with a toilet, 100% electrification, and safe and potable drinking water.

Congress has promised to give the right to housing to the urban poor. To secure universal access to toilets, the party proposes a 'Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan'.

While the Congress manifesto makes general promises on transport and logistics, the BJP's is more specific — 100 more functional airports, metro services in 100 cities, conversion of all railway lines to broad gauge, and a Bharatmala 2.0 to develop port capacities.

6. Employment

BJP party is promising to transform India into a global manufacturing hub by introducing an industrial policy that is aimed at harnessing emerging technologies, like artificial intelligence. Congress plans to fill all 4 lakh Central government and institutional vacancies before March 2020. Additionally, it has committed to pushing State governments to fill 20 lakh job vacancies. With a target of creating one crore jobs, Congress has promised a water bodies restoration mission and a 'wasteland regeneration mission' for low-skill workers. Congress also plans to link the definition of MSME to employment and to create an enterprise support agency to provide holistic support to entrepreneurs and start-ups.

A new ministry of industry, services, and employment will be created. The effective direct tax rate for companies that create jobs will be reduced. Additionally, the CSR fund contributions will be reduced. In the CSR rules, apprenticeship will be included.

7. Women

Financial empowerment of women is on the agenda of the BJP. Public procurement should be allocated to MSMEs who employ at least 50% women, childcare facilities will double by 2022, and a comprehensive 'Women in Workforce' strategy will be developed. As part of the BJP's plan, the party wants to reduce malnutrition in women and girls by 10 percent, create a Women's Security Division under the Home Ministry, and ban the Triple Talaq and Nikah Halala. Congress has promised to

establish working women's hostels and to provide safe transportation for women in every Special Economic Zone. It has also pledged to strictly enforce the Equal Remuneration Act and to eliminate laws prohibiting women from working night shifts. It's proposing to set up a separate investigative agency to investigate sexual crimes against women. While the BJP says it will provide sanitary pads at a flat rate of Rs. 1, Congress says it's planning vending machines in public places. The Congress and the BJP have both pledged 33 percent reservation for women in Parliament and Assemblies. Congress has also promised to amend the service rules to ensure one-third of appointments in the central government is for women.

8. Poverty

Poverty elimination is a top priority for both parties. Both parties have announced schemes that will help support extremely poor households in the country.

BJP has promised that it is committed to bringing down the percentage of families living below the poverty line to a single digit in the next five years.

It says that further steps will be taken to ensure access to bank branches, payment banks, and banking correspondents by creating a new "data-sharing privacy" framework that "builds on the success of Jan Dhan and Aadhaar platforms".

Meanwhile, the Congress party plans to "abject poverty" by 2030 and to introduce the Nyuntam Aay Yojana (NYAY) to provide Rs 72,000 a year to the 20 percent poorest families in the country. Around Rs 6,000 a month will be transferred to the account of a woman member of each family who is a part of the scheme.

9. Governance

Congress has vowed to pass an Anti-Discrimination Law, Councils for agriculture, healthcare and education, full statehood to Puducherry, Special Category Status to Andhra Pradesh, and characterize the role of Lieutenant Governors. For judicial reforms, it proposes to build up a National Judicial Commission, a Court of Appeal, an independent Judicial Complaints Commission, increase the representation of women and marginal sections at all levels of the judiciary.

The BJP wants to bring reforms in civil services along the lines of its "Minimum Government and Maximum Governance" motto. It also aspires to provide end-to-end digitization of government processes and digital delivery of government services. Establishing an International Financial Services Centre Authority is also on BJP's agenda.

The BJP wants to hold simultaneous elections for Parliament, Assemblies, and local bodies, while the Congress is prepared to scrap Electoral Bond Scheme and replace it with a National Election Fund.

10. Startups & Entrepreneurship

According to its BJP's manifesto, the party promises to launch a new scheme to provide collateral-free credit up to Rs 50 lakh for entrepreneurs. It will guarantee 50% of the loan amount for female entrepreneurs and 25% of the day loan amount for male entrepreneurs.

The Congress aims to set up a new "Entrepreneurial Northeast" scheme to provide financial support to the micro, small, and medium scale industries and enhance employment generation in the Northeast.

While BJP possesses a solid plan in place to boost startups in India, the Congress party has also left no stone unturned. The party said in its manifesto that it would create an Enterprise Support Agency to help entrepreneurs and start-ups with all-round support including counseling, incubation, and access to technology, funding, and many other purposes.

Congress has also promised to abolish Angel Tax imposed on start-ups.

References

(<https://manifesto.inc.in/pdf/english.pdf>)

(<https://library.bjp.org/jspui/bitstream/123456789/2988/1/BJP-Election-english-2019.pdf>)